

The Digital Periodontist: Augmenting Clinical Expertise with AI

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming various areas of healthcare, including periodontology, by improving diagnosis, treatment planning and patient care. Technologies powered by AI, such as machine learning, deep learning, and computer vision are used in areas like radiographic analysis, automated diseases detection and predicting the likely course of disease. These tools help detect periodontal diseases early and classify their severity accurately. AI has been successful in identifying and classifying the periodontal conditions, assessing the risk of disease, evaluating the bone levels, detecting halitosis, planning dental implants, identifying implant types, designing implants more effectively, predicting treatment results, and managing dental practices. AI can serve as a helpful aid for periodontists in making clinical decisions. There are certain limitations in their practical applications that need examined in future studies.

KEY WORDS: Artificial intelligence, Periodontology, Practical application

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is designed to create computer systems that can imitate human behavior using machines. In the fields of medicine and dentistry, as early as the 1970s, some experts predicted that AI would replace clinical roles; however, this has not come to pass. Periodontitis is one of the most common diseases globally. It is a type of inflammation that results from microbial activity and host response, leading to loss of alveolar bone and periodontal attachment, which can result in tooth loss. Clinicians often find it difficult to diagnose periodontitis accurately. Best practices include assessing soft tissues with a calibrated probe and examining hard tissues through radiographic imaging. However, these methods often lack consistency due to variations in probe pressure and radiographic angles. AI can be a valuable tool in analyzing these factors and enhancing understanding of disease diagnosis and causes [1,5].

ADVANCEMENTS IN DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES

AI technologies have significantly changed periodontal treatment by offering advanced data analysis to help clinicians make accurate diagnosis and plan effective treatment. New AI models can identify the development of periodontitis and allow for timely intervention and tailored treatment plans. Different fundamental AI models used in periodontal care are developed to serve various functions in diagnosis, classification and prognosis. The deep CNN model is effective in detecting damaged teeth, whereas U-Net and Mask R-CNN provide detailed outlines of periodontal structures, including the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone. The VGG-16 model predicts the severity of periodontal disease using clinical and radiographic features, and faster R-CNN precisely determines the extent of bone loss in radiographs. Collectively, these AI applications greatly improve periodontal assessments and treatment planning, proving AI's role in advancing periodontal care [6,7].

DIAGNOSIS AND PREDICTION OF PERIODONTALLY COMPROMISED TEETH

In 2018, Lee et al, introduced a computer-aided recognition system. A prelabelled periapical radiographic dataset was used to evaluate the diagnosis and predictability of periodontally compromised teeth [PCT]. The system achieved a diagnostic accuracy of 81.0% for premolars and 76.7% for molars, and a predictive accuracy of 82.8% for premolars and 73.4% for molars regarding extraction. The results of this study were comparable to those achieved by a board-certified periodontist [1].

APPLICATIONS IN IMPLANTOLOGY

Despite the growing demand for dental implants, many studies shows that not all implants are successful. In 2016, Sadat, Nazari et al, developed a hybrid method to predict the success of dental implants. They presented a combined predictive model using various classifiers such as neural networks, SVM, W-J48 and K-NN. The results showed that the performance of the combined classifiers was better than that of a single classifier, with an increase in sensitivity of up to 13.3%. the authors believe that this model can serve as a reliable tool for predicting implant success before the procedure [2]. In 2020, Lerner, Mouhyi et al introduced a protocol for using AI in the fabrication of implant -supported monolithic zirconia crowns [MZCs] attached to individual hybrid abutments. In this process, AI alongside CAD software was used

to create the crowns. This approach saved time, reduced the risk of errors, and lowered the costs of prosthetic treatment. A retrospective study of 106 implant-supported MZCs was conducted showing 3 year survival and success rates of 99.0% and 91.3% respectively [3]

Sometimes the dentist is unable to solve the implant – related issues of the patient as the implant system is unknown to the dentist. Therefore ,a need to identify the implant system without depending on the dentists knowledge or experience arose. Takahashi Nozaki et al.in 2020 successfully conducted a study using deep learning – based object detection software to identify implant systems from panoramic radiographs. The authors believe that this system could help dentists and patients alike suffering from implant – related issues [4].

RADIOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS:

Research highlights the potential of AI in diagnosing periodontal disease through radiographic analysis. Studies reveals that CNN models can automate the detection of radiographic bone loss [RBL] with accuracy rates between 63% and 99% depending on the type of radiograph analyzed. AI particularly CNN algorithms accurately detect and categorizes the severity of alveolar bone loss in periapical radiographs offering an efficient approach to periodontal disease detection and staging [5].

STAGING:

The application of AI can improve the accuracy of periodontitis staging .AI improves clinical data extraction and radiographs image interpretation by using machine learning algorithms and natural language processing, resulting in more accurate periodontal disease stage assessments . a through analysis found that deep learning methods improves periodontitis staging with good pooled sensitivity [0.88] and specificity [0.82] this technology helps dental professionals classify consistently saving workload and enhancing diagnostic reliability [6].

CONCLUSION

AI is transforming the field of dentistry by enhancing diagnostic accuracy, decision making , treatment planning and prognosis. AI can significantly reduce the workload of dental practitioners. Despite its advantages, AI cannot replace clinicians, but it is a valuable support tool. Periodontists and other dental professionals will continue to play a crucial role, utilizing their human skills to provide compassionate, patient centered care.

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